

Using ensemble learning to improve radiation tolerance of CNNs in space applications

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With the increasing complexity of space missions, improving the resilience of AI systems against radiation-induced errors is critical. This paper proposes the use of application-level optimizations of Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)-based systems to improve robustness in space applications without relying on expensive shielded electronics. In particular, our work demonstrates how a recently proposed methodology for zero-overhead ensembles of CNNs, named E²CNNs, can be applied to two case studies involving 6D pose estimation for satellite navigation. Our results show that E²CNNs achieves up to 5.48% higher accuracy compared to single-instance models under different error conditions, suggesting their effectiveness in improving resilience and output quality in low-earth orbit applications. The experimental evaluations indicate that even without memory protection, E²CNNs offers superior performance, making them a promising solution for AI-based space systems.

1 Introduction

Space missions are becoming increasingly important from both the scientific and economic points of view. For example, satellites are essential for numerous daily activities, including communications [1], navigation [2], weather forecasting [3] and prediction of natural disasters [4], remote sensing [5], and scientific research.

As mission complexity increases, the computing systems involved are following the same trends, and, hence, many of the technologies developed in the last years for Earth-bound applications are now being prepared for deployment in space applications. In particular, artificial intelligence (AI)-based systems are drawing increasing attention from both academia and

industry, as made evident during the “1st ESA Morpheus workshop on edge AI and neuromorphic hardware accelerators” [6].

Following such a direction, different plans have been announced for in-satellite processing of images (e.g., detection of objects of interest such as boats in the sea), hyperspectral image processing, star-based orientation, and even pose estimation for approximation to other objects. Many of these systems use convolutional neural networks (CNNs). Although CNNs are normally assumed to be naturally resilient to errors and data perturbations, their resilience is often not enough for the error rates found in space applications. Even worse, recent studies have shown that very small numbers of errors can completely change the outcome of CNN inference, making their behavior too unpredictable [7]. To alleviate this, CNN robustness can be increased by implementing different solutions, either at the hardware level (e.g., electronic shielding), or at the application level. In the latter case, CNN models can be combined together in ensembles that achieve higher accuracy and robustness than single-instance CNNs, but typically increase memory requirements and computing workloads.

This work aims to improve the error resilience of AI-based space applications by transforming the baseline single-instance CNN model into an equivalent set of smaller and derived models or ensembles, inspired by [8] and named E²CNNs. Ensembles increase the resilience of the original CNN design because they add spatial and/or temporal redundancy: Sequential execution of the different components of the ensemble reduces the relevance of single event upsets (SEUs); separate storage or parallel computation of the ensemble components confines the impact of permanent errors to one of the elements of the ensemble. In con-

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trast to traditional ensembles, E²CNNs was originally presented in the environment of resource-constrained embedded systems with focus on maintaining the computational requirements of the original networks.

On this basis, in this work, we apply the concept of E²CNNs to two CNNs designed to calculate 6D pose estimation for the navigation control of satellites. Our results evidence the effectiveness of E²CNNs in improving accuracy and robustness in space-related applications at the typical error rates found in Low-Earth-Orbit (LEO) applications, thus suggesting their use in place of well-known single-instance models.

The rest of this document is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses related work in the context of AI-based space applications, CNNs and ensembles. The different case studies tackled in this work are addressed in Section 3, followed by the experimental setup in Section 4. Results are shown and thoroughly discussed in Section 5 and future research directions are proposed in Section 6.

2 Ensembling CNNs for AI-based applications in space

Ensembling CNNs is an application-level transformation that combines several models, aggregating their predictions to obtain more accurate outputs [9]. Although very effective at improving accuracy, such a solution can dramatically increase computational and memory requirements, since multiple models must be stored and executed at runtime. An alternative to traditional ensembling methods is E²CNNs, a methodology that transforms a single-instance CNN model into an ensemble-based equivalent [8], where the generated ensembles do not exhibit any memory or computational overhead with respect to the initial model. However, the combination of multiple instances in E²CNNs increases accuracy and robustness when properly dimensioned.

Figure 1 summarizes the E²CNNs methodology. The first step towards the construction of the constrained ensemble is a compression phase, where the baseline CNN structure is reduced in size and complexity via filter pruning. The obtained pruned structure can then be replicated multiple times. When the compression factor C and the replication factor R (also known as the *cardinality of the ensemble*) are equal, the obtained ensemble and the baseline CNN model have the same computational requirements. Each structure is then independently trained on the target dataset. When starting from a random weight initialization, this training approach generates different weight distributions across the CNN instances of

Figure 1: E²CNNs methodology. The baseline CNN model is first compressed. Then, the obtained structure is replicated multiple times to build an ensemble. The individual training procedures result in different weights distributions among the replicated instances, ultimately improving accuracy and robustness.

E²CNNs. This variability is key to improving accuracy and robustness. When performing inference tasks, the same input sample is fed to each CNN composing the E²CNNs ensemble, and individual predictions are then averaged to compute the E²CNNs output. This approach offers higher accuracy and better low-cardinality ensembles (e.g., 2 or 4 instances only) [8]. Although E²CNNs robustness has been assessed in the presence of memory errors, its resiliency in radiation environments has not been demonstrated yet. In this work, we employ E²CNNs in the design of our benchmarks, using the heuristic illustrated in [8] to determine the optimal E²CNNs cardinality. As investigated in previous works [10], floating-point formats are particularly sensitive to perturbations because errors affecting bits of the exponent may introduce dramatic magnitude changes, significantly degrading accuracy. Therefore, we employ a fixed-point representation in our experiments, using 16 and 32 bits for weights and activations, respectively. In our experiments, such a quantization scheme does not introduce appreciable accuracy degradation with respect to the corresponding floating-point models.

3 Case studies

Along with the increasing use of satellites, there has also been an accumulation of non-operational satellites and other types of debris around Earth [11]. This debris, which includes discarded rocket stages, broken satellites, and fragments generated by collisions, poses a serious threat to space activities. There are currently more than 3000 non-functional satellites in orbit, along with tens of thousands of smaller objects. On the one hand, these objects may collide with active satellites, possibly causing damages that prevent users on Earth from benefiting from certain services. On the other hand, collisions may result in the generation of additional debris, potentially making some orbits unusable for decades or even centuries. The success of debris removal programs requires both precise and robust navigation systems, and accurate object-tracking routines. Several AI-based proposals

have been made in the state-of-the-art (SoA) to identify and track debris in space. In particular, several CNN-based systems have been proposed to perform 6D pose estimation, a process that determines the position and orientation of a 3D object in a 3D environment [12].

6D pose estimation is a key task for the navigation control of satellites that try to approach space debris. In fact, an incorrect pose estimation may result in ineffective debris grappling, potentially leading to system damage and the creation of additional debris due to the high speeds (and therefore energies) involved. In this context, a recent study focused on this challenge [13], showcasing the different contrasts, exposures, and brightness of images collected in space compared to typical benchmarks in the field of computer vision. In addition, this work proposed a novel CNN-based design to improve the output quality of pose estimation in space applications. We consider this proposal as one of the two case studies in this work to assess the effectiveness of E²CNNs in improving the resilience of CNNs in space applications.¹ To this end, we consider the WDRNet network used in [13].

As a second case study, we consider a SoA architecture in the field of computer vision named SPNv2, developed at the Space Rendezvous Laboratory (SLAB) of Stanford University [14]. Both architectures share a similar structure and common blocks. In particular, each model consists of three CNN-based components, namely, backbone, FPN, and HEAD. Table 1 summarizes their main structural characteristics. Although WDRNet uses the backbone presented in [13] and is based on the Tiny DarkNet architecture [15], SPNv2 employs EfficientNet-B2 [16] as the backbone component. To accomplish the same 6D pose estimation task, the same HEAD module is used in both implementations. We employ the methodology described in [8] to determine the E²CNNs cardinality for the considered use cases and, in both cases, we derive 2-instance E²CNNs implementations. Both E²CNNs implementations are trained and tested on a synthetic dataset, generated from proprietary ESA camera images. The dataset is divided into 27 000 training, 1 000 validation, and 2 000 testing images.

4 Experimental Setup

In our experiments, we assume that the network will be executed on an SRAM-based FPGA. Radiation-induced SEUs are simulated at the application level by randomly injecting errors in weight and activation values. These events may occur anytime during CNN

Table 1: Overview of the structure of the evaluated CNNs

WDRNet			
	# layers	Size (MiB)	GFLOPs
Backbone	15	1.75	2.4
FPN	6	4.1	3.3
HEAD	60	36.3	25.8
SPNv2			
	# layers	Size (MiB)	GFLOPs
Backbone	22	4.7	1.2
FPN	6	6.3	2.8
HEAD	60	36.3	25.8

inference. Therefore, we simulate the possible impact of SEUs in any multiply-accumulate (MAC) operation, allowing errors to appear whenever a data word is read from memory. We assume that program memory is protected (e.g., with ECC) since errors affecting program instructions can have unpredictable critical effects and should thus be avoided. Consequently, we focus on errors affecting the FPGA BRAM (SRAM) data memory. SEUs are introduced by randomly flipping one bit of the read memory word, randomly affecting bits of input operands in all MAC operations. As a consequence, each input data sample may be affected differently. Errors affecting the most significant bits (MSBs) of either weights or activations may introduce larger deviations from the expected behavior than errors affecting the least significant bits (LSBs) of the same memory words. We account for this effect by running multiple inferences over the whole testing dataset. While instruction memory is assumed to be protected, data memory protection might be implemented or not. In our experiments, we consider both scenarios. In particular, we assume that weights stored in BRAM can always be affected by errors, but their value is refreshed every time they are re-fetched from flash memory. Conversely, activations stored in DRAM can either be protected (e.g., using ECC), or not. We also assume that the internal storage elements of the FPGA, such as LUT contents and the control of interconnections, are protected. However, they represent a negligible fraction of the considered memory system, and studying the effects of radiation on these elements is out of the scope of this work.

We assume an expected error rate E_{exp} due to radiation in Earth's low orbit of 10^{-5} errors/bit-day [17]. Assuming a worst-case inference execution time T_{run} of two seconds and worst-case memory requirements M_{size} of 66 MiB, we compute the average number of errors per inference as follows:

$$E_{inf} = \frac{E_{exp} T_{run} M_{size}}{86\,400}, \quad (1)$$

where M_{size} must be expressed in units of bits and

¹<https://github.com/cvlab-epfl/wide-depth-range-pose>

86 400 is the number of seconds in a day. The result is an average number of expected errors per inference of 1.62×10^{-2} . This result indicates that we could reasonably assume just 1 bit flipping every 62 inferences.

Taking into account the number of MAC operations and the number of memory accesses per inference, we convert the computed error rate into the error probability of having a bit flipped in any data word read from memory. We, therefore, obtain an error rate per word around 10^{-10} . The probability of having multiple errors in the same memory word is negligible in practice; thus, we do not consider this possibility in our error model. Nevertheless, to consider more adverse scenarios, we consider both the expected 10^{-10} and a more aggressive 10^{-8} bit error rates.

A C++ CNN inference solver was developed to simulate fixed-point arithmetic, reflecting real hardware computations, and to inject radiation-induced errors in weights and activations during MACs. Weights and activations were constrained to 16 and 32-bit fixed-point formats, respectively. Finally, the results of the CNN inference were integrated into a PyTorch-based framework to evaluate their 6D pose estimation accuracy at different depth ranges. We consider the standard ADI.10d metric, which measures the percentage of samples for which the 3D reconstruction error is below 10 % of the object diameter [13]. We also evaluate different thresholds (i.e., ADI.01d to ADI.50d) in our work.

5 Results and Discussion

In this following, we present an analysis in which we first compare the precision of the single-instance benchmarks with that achieved by the corresponding alternatives E²CNNs, in an error-free setting. Table 2-*top* summarizes the pose estimation accuracy at different ADI thresholds. Our results confirm the conclusions presented in [8], demonstrating that, even without errors, the E²CNNs designs perform better than their single-instance baselines. Taking into account the standard evaluation metric ADI.10d, our experiments show average accuracy improvements of 1.95 % and 3.60 %, respectively, for WDRNet and SPNv2.

E²CNNs is then evaluated in the presence of memory errors, assuming that the FPGA BRAM is protected using ECC (Table 2-*middle*). We observe that ECC can significantly limit accuracy degradation to less than 1 % in the E²CNNs and the single-instance models for the two error rates. As a consequence, the initial higher accuracy of E²CNNs allows this solution to achieve higher accuracy even in the presence of memory errors, with average improvements of 1.85 % and 2.45 % for an ADI.10d threshold, at error rates of

Table 2: Accuracy of baseline models and of the proposed E²CNNs system at different error rates.

Error-free Results	
	ADI.01d .03d .05d .10d .15d .30d .50d
WDRNet	0.70 15.45 32.10 55.65 69.80 87.30 92.75
E ² CNNs	0.90 19.30 35.50 57.60 69.70 87.35 92.70
SPNv2	0.60 13.45 29.50 53.95 65.80 83.20 91.85
E ² CNNs	1.00 17.65 36.60 57.55 68.75 83.60 89.55
ECC Protection, Error rate 10^{-10}	
	ADI.01d .03d .05d .10d .15d .30d .50d
WDRNet	0.70 15.60 32.00 55.70 69.80 87.20 92.70
E ² CNNs	0.95 19.25 35.70 57.55 69.60 87.25 92.90
SPNv2	0.86 13.20 29.01 52.74 65.22 82.65 90.95
E ² CNNs	1.26 15.35 33.51 56.85 68.39 83.14 89.47
ECC Protection, Error rate 10^{-8}	
	ADI.01d .03d .05d .10d .15d .30d .50d
WDRNet	0.95 15.50 31.20 54.45 68.30 85.70 91.85
E ² CNNs	0.75 19.05 35.00 56.90 69.45 87.10 92.55
SPNv2	0.97 13.02 28.88 52.69 65.51 82.68 90.89
E ² CNNs	0.72 15.30 30.91 54.78 65.73 83.11 89.26
No Protection, Error rate 10^{-10}	
	ADI.01d .03d .05d .10d .15d .30d .50d
WDRNet	0.70 14.50 30.60 54.40 68.50 86.05 91.80
E ² CNNs	0.90 19.45 35.25 57.60 69.65 87.30 92.80
SPNv2	0.67 12.71 28.31 51.56 63.79 82.41 90.79
E ² CNNs	0.39 15.44 31.99 55.41 66.43 82.76 88.96
No Protection, Error rate 10^{-8}	
	ADI.01d .03d .05d .10d .15d .30d .50d
WDRNet	0.65 14.16 29.43 50.87 63.94 79.70 84.95
E ² CNNs	1.00 18.85 34.90 56.35 68.70 86.75 92.40
SPNv2	0.62 10.49 24.01 51.19 63.77 79.07 87.21
E ² CNNs	0.41 13.15 29.37 54.35 64.36 82.33 87.20

10^{-10} and 10^{-8} , respectively.

Finally, we have run experiments without ECC, so that both weights and activations can be affected by memory errors. Table 2-*bottom* shows that the single-instance model exhibited significant accuracy drops, especially at an error rate of 10^{-8} . In contrast, even with no memory protection, E²CNNs is able to maintain the initial accuracy well, demonstrating the high robustness of this solution. On average, considering again an ADI.10d threshold, E²CNNs offers an accuracy 3.20 % and 5.48 % higher than the single-instance model, respectively, for the two error rates. These results indicate that E²CNNs outperforms the accuracy of the single-instance model, without increasing the baseline memory and computing requirements.

Our results suggest that the robustness of E²CNNs supports high-quality 6D pose estimations at rela-

tively low error rates expected in low-orbit space applications without the need for memory ECC protection, thus improving performance and energy consumption. In the worst-case scenario, where no protection is adopted and at an error rate of 10^{-8} , E²CNNs can still offer an accuracy *improvements* of 0.55 % compared to the single instance baselines evaluated under error-free conditions. In contrast, baseline models exhibit accuracy *degradation* higher than 3.5 %.

6 Future Works

We envision multiple research directions to extend this work. First, we plan to implement the discussed E²CNNs design on FPGAs, to evaluate the runtime and energy benefits of the proposed approach. This analysis will enable a clearer understanding of computing bottlenecks and energy expenditure in the proposed design. In this regard, we consider improving the proposed solution by combining CNN architectures with Vector Symbolic Architectures (VSA), such as Hyperdimensional Computing (HDC) [18]. Including HDC could offer several benefits in the considered application: first, high-dimensional vector representations exhibit significantly higher error resiliency than CNN models, hence improving the radiation tolerance of the proposed navigation system. Second, HDC enables lightweight element-wise operations for both inference and training. On the one hand, computing and energy requirements can be easily improved, especially when processing in memory (PIM) accelerators are considered [19]. On the other hand, the limited training complexity of HDC makes online retraining feasible, thus opening the path for model fine-tuning and adaptation to unseen environments. This capability could also be leveraged in the future to extend AI-based intelligent systems currently used in several space applications.

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